

GRAPE PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION IN UZBEKISTAN: CURRENT PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract. This article analyzing the current situation of viticulture in Uzbekistan, as well as the industry's difficulties and their solutions. Uzbekistan is geographically placed in the "wine belt" - the globe's parallel. This enables not just the production of table grape varieties for export and domestic consumption, but also the entry into European markets of new global trends, such as valuable non-alcoholic wines made from high-quality industrial varieties. This is accomplished through R&D research and development in this field. Their uvological research on grapes from the collections of the M. Mirzaev Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture, and Winemaking and the Scientific Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources of Uzbekistan allows us to study the composition of industrial grape varieties more deeply, expand the assortment of varieties, describing and evaluation of native grape varieties grown in Uzbekistan for the production of grape products with high bioactive and nutritional value. The end goal of our scientific research is to produce foods with improved nutritious content, exportable products with an added value chain based on new technologies, and a well-researched raw material base.

Keywords: viticulture, grape, varieties, uvology, ampelography

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston uzumchiligining bugungi ahvoli, sohadagi mavjud muammolar va ularning yechimlarini tahlil qilingan. O'zbekiston geografik joylashuviga ko'ra yer sharining "uzumchilik belbog'i" ya'ni paralellida joylashgan. Bu esa nafaqat exportbop va mahalliy iste'mol uchun xo'raki uzum navlarini yetishtirish, balki yuqori sifatli sanoatbop navlardan qiymati yuqori, alkogolsiz vino kabi jahon trendidagi yangi mahsulotlar bilan Evropa bozorlariga chiqish imkonini beradi. Bunga esa sohada R&D tadqiqotlar olib borilishi orqali erishiladi. Tadqiqotlar M. Mirzaev nomidagi bog'dorchilik, uzumchilik va vinochilik ilmiy-tadqiqot instituti va O'zbekiston o'simliklar genetik resurslari ilmiy-tadqiqot instituti kolleksiyalaridagi uzumlarga asoslangan holda ularni uvologik tadqiq qilish, sanoatbop uzum navlari tarkibini chuqur o'rganish, assortimentini kengaytirish, biologik faol moddalarga boy navlarni aniqlash imkonini beradi. Chuqur o'rganilgan hom ashyo bazasiga asoslangan holda yangi texnologiyalar asosida aholi salomatligiga foydali, eksportbop, qushimcha qiymat zanjiriga ega mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish barcha ilmiy tadqiqotlarning pirovard natijasidir.

Kalit so'zlar: uzumchilik, uzum navlari, uvologiya, ampelografiya

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется современное состояние виноградарства Узбекистана, существующие проблемы в отрасли и их решения. Узбекистан по своему географическому положению находится в так называемом "виноградарском поясе" - параллели земного шара. Это позволяет не только выращивать столовые сорта винограда для экспорта и местного потребления, но и выходить на европейские рынки с новыми мировыми тенденциями, такими как дорогостоящие безалкогольные вина из высококачественных промышленных сортов. И это достигается за счет исследований и разработок в этой области. Исследования, основываясь на виноградах из коллекций научно-исследовательского института садоводства, виноградарства и виноделия им. М.Мирзаева и Научно-исследовательского института генетических ресурсов растений Узбекистана, их uvологические исследование позволяет глубже изучить состав промышленных сортов

винограда, расширить ассортимент, выявить сорта, богатые биологически активными веществами. Производство продуктов питания повышенной пищевой ценностью, экспортбельных продуктов с добавленной цепочкой стоимости на основе новых технологий, глубоко изученной сырьевой базы является конечным результатом всех научных исследований.

Ключевые слова: виноградарство, сорта винограда, увология, ампелография

Introduction. Viticulture is one of the most ancient and at the same time one of the most profitable branches of Uzbekistan's agriculture. Therefore, country regularly pays special attention to the sustainable development of viticulture in the Republic and the radical increase in the production of exportable grape products [1]. In particular, as stated in the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on July 7, 2021, dedicated to the issues of growing grapes, developing their industrial processing, and establishing enotourism in the regions, "Viticulture is the centuries-old national farming culture, value, pride and is a source of income. Grapes are directly connected with the lifestyle and traditions of our people. There was a vine on every street and in every house. The quality of our grapes such as Husayni, Toyfi, Rizamat, Kelin barmog and Kishmish is known far and wide" [2]. During this speech, proposals and instructions were given to establish the storage and processing of agricultural products in the country, to create a national brand of grape varieties of our country and promote them abroad, to expand the range of agricultural products, to reach international standards agreements with potential markets.

Uzbekistan is one of the largest grape-growing countries in the world and, according to statistics, ranked 12th. The total volume of grape growing (food, fruit and technical) is 1,978 million tons, the yield is 16 tons/ha. The total area of vineyards in the country is 148.9 thousand hectares, in the last four years, new vineyards were established on 52 thousand hectares, and 210 billion soums of subsidies were allocated to the sector. As a result, the share of grapes in the export of fruits and vegetables has doubled. During the last two years, 44 districts of Uzbekistan have been directed to viticulture, and it is planned to breed especially technical grape varieties in these areas [5, 10]. In the coming years, the further increase of the area of vineyards is set separately. This trend of increasing the area of vineyards is directly related to the internal and external demand for grapes and grape products. Demand for grape products (wine, vinegar, grape molasses, etc.) in Uzbekistan is increasing year by year.

It should be noted that the domestic demand for most products obtained from grapes (wine, raisins) is fully satisfied by the volume of local production. However, the production of consumer products such as grape vinegar, grape molasses, grape juice is organized on a very small scale, and a significant part of the demand for these products is met at the expense of imports. Domestic demand for products such as grape fruitade [4] and grape vinegar, which have a particularly high nutritional value, is increasing sharply. Therefore, scientific justification of the production of the above-mentioned products from local grape varieties is one of the most important tasks today [9]. For this, it is necessary to conduct a deep analysis of local technical varieties that allow obtaining high-quality exportable grape products, to determine the amount of biologically active substances in their clusters, and on this basis to conduct scientific research on obtaining valuable and environmentally friendly grape products rich in bioactive compounds.

Discuss. As we mentioned above, in recent years special attention has been paid to the development of the grape processing industry and the radical increase in the production of exportable raisins, wine brands and other products. It is known that the quality of grape processing

products (wine, raisins, grape molasses, grape vinegar, etc.) is directly related to the biochemical composition of the raw material - grape berries. It is known that the quality of wine is directly related to the raw material - biochemical composition of grape berries.

High-quality processed products can be produced only from grape varieties rich in total sugar, organic acids, phenol and dyes and other biologically active substances and compounds [5, 6].

It should be noted separately that although the collection of grape varieties in the country is more than 1,800 grape processing products are produced based on only about 50 grape varieties are produced in Uzbekistan and most of them are table grapes for fresh consumption and seedless grapes for drying purposes (*Figure 2*). In particular, technical varieties such as Bayan Shirey, Rkatsiteli, Aleatico, Cabernet sauvignon, Kuldzhin are used in the preparation of wine products, raisin varieties such as Qora Kishmish, Kishmish Sogdiana, Oq kishmish are used for raisin production, and raisin varieties such as Sultani are used for raisin production. Such a small size of the assortment of processed varieties can be directly explained by the fact that the biochemical composition of the cluster of local grape varieties of grapes has not been thoroughly studied in our country. In-depth analysis of the composition and amount of valuable biologically active substances in the grape berries, relevant for table variety and wine grapes and creating the new wine brands and other exportable grape products on this basis, also, the amount of scientific research carried out on the improvement of grape processing technologies by applying innovative technologies cannot be considered sufficient [8].

Figure 2. Types of grape varieties grown in Uzbekistan

The book "*Ampelography of Uzbekistan*", which is used as a guide in many vineyards, wineries and grape processing industries, was published in 1984 [6]. As we mentioned above, although there are more than 1,800 varieties of grapes collected in the collections of the Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources of Uzbekistan and its regional experimental stations and grown by the local population, the characteristics, biological, technological features, mechanical properties of only 165 varieties are described in this book. information about its composition and economic importance is given [6]. In addition, today most of these varieties are outdated and removed from the current state register [15]. Also, during the past 39 years, the assortment of grapes of Uzbekistan has been enriched with new selective and introduced varieties, and the study

of their biological, technological features and biochemical composition is important for the viticulture and winemaking industry.

It is clear that more than 1000 varieties of grapes, which have been cultivated for a long time, local, newly created selective and introduced, need to be studied in depth biochemically. Local grape varieties that are planned to be studied within the framework of the project will be analyzed in depth, and the determination of indicators such as the content of biologically active substances, the amount of complex polyphenol compounds and antioxidant activity will allow the creation of promising and competitive processed grape products (wine, grape vinegar, grape molasses, etc.).

In recent years, the modern wine trends in the world are changing. Wine industry is very concerned health prevention policies and is therefore interested in wines with a moderate alcohol level. People who choose a healthy lifestyle prefer to drink non-alcoholic drinks. The producing of dealcoholized wines or beverages obtained by wine dealcoholization could be a viable alternative for minimizing alcohol use or introducing new products to the market for those who are unable to drink alcohol for a variety of reasons (e.g., religion, diet, at work, etc.). It is apparent that the demand for non-alcoholic beverages has increased significantly during the previous several years.

The amount of phenolic compounds in the grape berries depends on the area of growing, climate, soil, and biochemical characteristics of the variety [3, 9] Selection of samples that will allow preparation of high-quality wine intended for export based on an in depth study of the collection of local wine grape varieties in our country is of great importance in increasing the efficiency of winemaking. In recent years, in our country and abroad, it has been recognized that electrophysical effects give more positive results in accelerating the extraction of fluids (juice) inside and between cells from biological materials and products, in achieving biological and chemical positive changes in the juice [9, 12-14] Electrophysical effects include electric current, electric field and magnetic field currents, impulsing electrical discharge, ultrasonic wave energy, etc. Based on the intended purpose of use, the above-mentioned electrophysical effects are used in various technological processes in the food industry. Wine is made from the local Muskat Ranniy Cherniy, Muskat VIRa, Kora Janjal, Rangdor, Guzal Kora, Magarachsky wine grape varieties grown in Tashkent and Samarkand regions by the micro-winemaking method, and it is desirable to analyze the activity of phenolic compounds and antioxidants in wines at different stages of fermentation, to determine the amount of bioactive compounds and to observe the dynamics of their changes.

It is known that biologically active substances such as Trans-Resveratrol and vitamins are important substances that determine the quality of wine. These substances play an important role in human health. S.Kh.Abdurazakova, U.K. Abdullaev, M.M. Scientific winemaking issue studies were carried out by such scientists as Mirzaev, Kh.Abdullaev, V.Ivanchenko, A.Arzumanov. [8]. However, the research of these scientists is mainly limited to agro-technologies of growing wine grape varieties and some winemaking issues, and it is important to carry out extensive scientific research in the direction of winemaking technology improvement based on local varieties.

Conclusion. The diet and way of life are directly related to the cardiovascular, liver-bile, gastrointestinal, general malaise, and other diseases that have recently been observed in people of various ages. It is no secret that the Central Asian especially Uzbek people eat a lot of fatty, heavily fried, and difficult-to-digest dishes (somsa, manti, pilaf, jiz, kasan kebab, and so on). Nowadays, energy drinks with high levels of carbonation are now being consumed a lot. However, the large

consumption of these drinks by younger generations in areas where alcoholic beverages are not prescribed exacerbates the health problem noted above. Both drinks and the earlier mentioned foods have very low levels of physiologically active chemicals and vitamins. On the other hand, there is a relatively limited supply of beverages made for younger demographics of the population that are high in biologically active chemicals. As a result, the construction of natural grape juices and non-alcoholic wine product production in Uzbekistan is regarded as one of the promising and important fields. The nation has an enough supply of raw materials to produce these goods. In addition, more research and development (R&D), new processing technologies, sustainable storage technologies, and a review of worldwide experience will be with the goal to establish practices that improve production efficiency and grape product quality with high bioactive components and natural ingredients.

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